

TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF STAFF PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY MANAGEMENT

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Article Info

Keywords: Development, Productivity, Staff, Training, University

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.13744578

Abstract

This article examined the impact of management evaluation on the training and development of staff productivity, with a particular focus on the Nigerian University system. The objectives were: to examine the personnel policy of the Nigerian University system, assess the extent to which the personnel policy has been implemented by the university, and identify the challenges faced by university management in the training and development of Staff for improved productivity. These also defined the scope and limitations of the study. The research design and methodology adopted a doctrinal approach using analytical and descriptive research methodology. The primary and secondary sources of data collection were physical and e-library sources. It was found that the personnel policy of most Nigerian Universities is not within the reach of the Staff of the University, it does not benefit the Staff of the University, and it does not positively influence Staff productivity; also that the University management does not carry out effective implementation and monitoring of the personnel policy concerning the staff of the University, and university management lacks equity in the training and development of Staff productivity. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the university senate should amend the personnel policy of the respective Nigerian university to be accordingly impactful on staff development and productivity. Moreover, the personnel policy should be made available for staff to work toward its development and productivity.

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1. Introduction

Human resources in manpower or staff are considered the most critical to any university's survival, which of a truism involves an adequate supply of material and financial resources for the utilization of the available resources to achieve the desired goals. However, most university management plans meticulously for their investments in physical and capital resources, and these plans are reviewed with utmost attention to detail, whereas rarely do such universities pay attention to staff investment in which the capital and equipment will be in vain. Not many universities consider the necessity for well-defined and sustained staff training and development to upgrade their performance or are not able to cope financially with training and development programs.

The very few universities that give thought to this critical aspect of staffing functions do so with a lack of seriousness, attention and continuity. Programs are seldom conducted and are lopsided in terms of content and staff participation. Because of this, a lackadaisical attitude of management toward training and development of staff results in reduced productivity. There has been a progressive decline in the ability of manpower to cope with the challenges that attend to the unfolding new dispensation in universities. In this circumstance, what we find is that the rise in academic output is inconsequential despite the enormous wave of modern technology that now exists in academic activities.

Staff members leave their universities because they are not developed and sufficiently motivated. Some are not willing to leave because they enjoy benefits in terms of training and promotion, which lead to increases in salaries, wages, bonuses, and other incentives. Universities should improve the work performance, training, productivity, skills, and abilities of their employees. Thus, one of the major problems is developing and motivating workers to achieve higher productivity.

Therefore, training and development must be a continuous process as a means of enhancing the acquisition and improvement of new skills and knowledge. However, the problem shows that the cost of training and development does not yield commensurate results. Therefore, it is pertinent for university management to evaluate its training and development programs with a view to determine their impact on staff productivity. This, therefore, is also the problem propelling the choice of this topic. Furthermore, it is obvious that the poor performance of university staff follows from their inability to keep abreast with the new technological current as a result of the absence of appropriate and sufficient staff training, development and evaluation. It is against this backdrop that this article aims to examine the impact of Management evaluation on the training and development of staff productivity in Nigeria.

2. Conceptual Analysis

2.1 Management Evaluation

Most writers have concerned themselves with putting forward arguments for and against the very idea of management evaluation and development in organizations. Some authors have emphasized the need for management evaluation and how to ensure increased efficiency and productivity by using manpower plans and development programs. Thomas Kempwer (1971:13) views management evaluation as the name given to the development of different types of assessment and valuation of manpower that the University will require over a period of years. He believes that once a University has developed a long-range strategy (corporate planning), it becomes possible to estimate the number of people of all types and categories that may be required over the following years.

Olusola Aina (1992:68) defined management evaluation or human resource planning as a possible endeavor for determining and assuring that an organization will have an adequate number of skilled and experienced

individuals available at the right time and place to perform jobs that meet the needs of the organization and that provides satisfaction for the workers involved. Management evaluation of providing an adequate number of skilled workers is expected to provide job satisfaction to those workers in return. Ubeku Abel (1975:25) defined management evaluation as part of organizational planning. He observed that it should therefore be seen not in isolation but in the entire context of the growth of the organization. According to him, management evaluation covers more than simple planning of the future manpower requirements of an organization since it hinges on all aspects of the business.

This approach goes beyond mere consideration of supply but is not specific to other aspects of business manpower. It also comes with the impression that the only concrete matter it deals with is the future supply of labor. Oliver Ibekwe (1984:19) asserted that the human resources of a business are collectively known as manpower, which could be unskilled, skilled, or supervisory staff, and it is aimed at ensuring that the right person is available for the job at the right time. Quest et al. (1969) saw management evaluation to integrate personnel policies and plan various personnel activities, such as recruitment, training, management development, payment, and industrial relations.

The management and leadership development process is flexible and continuous, linking individual development to job and organization goals. Management development programs on campus give students the opportunity to develop a broad base of skills and knowledge that can be applied to many jobs. The university management development curriculum is changing. The overarching goal is a comprehensive curriculum for managers and supervisors to develop the core competencies required to become excellent leaders.

2.2 Staff Training

Training, according to the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, is the process of preparing someone for a job. In human resource development, training is therefore an indispensable element and, at the same time, a vehicle for development and planning. Fanibuyan (2001) defined training as the systematic process of altering the behavior and/or attitudes of employees in a direction to increase organizational goals and development as a program generally aimed at educating supervisory employees above and beyond the immediate technical requirements of the job and has the main objective of improving the effective performance of all managers. Training is the application of knowledge and experience (Punia&Saurabh, 2013). Training can be defined as an organized activity aimed at imparting information and/or instructions to improve the recipient's performance or to help the recipient attain a required level of knowledge or skill (Appiah et al, 2013).

According to Stemetz et al. (1969:68), training is a short-term process that utilizes a systematic and organized procedure by which non-managerial personnel learn technical knowledge that is skilled for a certain period. Thus, training is technically oriented. It is designed to improve the technical and mechanical skills of personnel. Training is therefore usually designed for both non-managerial and managerial staff. Dorman Price (1975:572) emphasized the role of training in management activities, especially in the area of human resources management. According to him, the training function is a management activity in which the personnel department provides the necessary specialist knowledge and usually undertakes this in addition to administrative requirements so that the training function operates effectively within the organization. He further stated the basic stages in establishing training functions with the aim of improving manpower development.

These stages are described as follows:

- a) To determine the training needs of the particular needs of the university at all levels.
- b) Formulating a training policy that will meet the needs of the organization.
- c) To evaluate both financial and material resources that could be required.

d) Provide the necessary specialist training officers, who will be responsible for implementing both the training policy and training plan.

Training needs can be said to exist when there is a gap between the existing performance of an employee (or group of employees) and the desired performance to assess whether such a gap requires skill analysis. The analysis proceeds in five stages. They are:

- a) To analyze and determine the main requirements of a particular job.
- b) To identify tasks required to meet job requirements.
- c) Understanding the procedures required to perform the task.
- d) To analyze the knowledge and skills required to perform the processes.
- e) To identify and specify tasks and analyze any particular skills required to solve the problem.

However, if we consider a situation where not training function exists in the organization, the skills analysis should be undertaken initially for these jobs or areas, which appear to present the most urgent training needs, and this can be followed by a skill analysis of all jobs when the training function has been established.

In a nutshell, training is the organized way in which organizations provide development and enhance the quality of new and existing staff. Training is viewed as a systematic approach of learning and development that improves individuals, groups, and organizations (Goldstein& Ford, 2002) in Khawaja & Nadeem (2013). Thus, it is the series of activities undertaken by an organization that leads to knowledge or skills acquisition for growing purposes, thereby contributing to the well-being and performance of human capital, the organization, as well as the society at large. According to Manju and Suresh (2011), training serves as an act of intervention to improve an organization's goods and services quality to stiff competition by improving the technical skills of its employees.

2.3 Staff Development

Development generally means the process of causing somebody or something to grow or make something gradually to become larger. In relation to manpower development, it can be seen as a process of increasing the quality, value, or skill of an employee (personnel). Development involves preparing future employees for higher responsibilities. Development according to Ezeuwa (2009) can be seen as the use of human resources to quantitatively change a person's physical and biological environments for their benefit or as involving the introduction of new ideas into the social structure and causing alterations to the patterns of the organization and social structure. To develop staff, (Daniels, 2003) simply refers to making them grow with the company so that they can be fitted for available higher positions within their capacity. Development involves improving human relations and interpersonal (Ekaterini, 2009).

From the definition, it can be concluded that training facilitates manpower development and consequently performance. Manpower training and development are two inter-related processes whose importance cannot be overemphasized in any strategic human resource management decision. These are related to the series of activities that an enterprise undertakes to improve the quality of its managerial capacity. In this view of Jelena, J. S. (2007:204) stated that manpower development refers broadly to the nature and direction of change induced in employees because of educating and training programs. He asserts that development is managerial in nature and career-focused.

In summary, development refers to activities leading to the acquisition of new knowledge or skills for growth. Organizations provide employees with development programs in order to enhance their capabilities. Employee development is gaining an increasingly critical and strategic imperative in organizations in the current business

environment (Sheri-lyne 2007) in Abdul Hameed (2011). Thus, organizations need to invest in continuous employee development to maintain employees and achieve organizational success (Khawaja & Nadeem 2013).

2.4 Training and Development of Staff

Obviously, as jobs become increasingly complex, it becomes imperative for labor employers to train their workers, unlike when jobs were simple and required little technical knowledge from the workers. Staff development has been described as a systematic process that an organization has to go through to ensure that it has effective managers to meet its present and future needs. Staff training and development are two interrelated processes whose importance cannot be overemphasized in any discussion of strategic human resource management. This is related to the series of activities that an enterprise would need to embark upon to improve the quality of its managerial capital.

According to De Philips et al (1964:8), training is a process when under university auspices seeks a planned, coordinated, and conscious manner to develop in the employees the understanding skills and attitude that will maximize an individual's present and future efficiency and effectiveness in the overall University operations. To distinguish staff training and development, Chanokan has this to say, "that unlike the training, the workers which improves technical and mechanical skills, development techniques are designed for work behavior modification". According to him, development is an educational process that utilizes a systematic organizational procedure by which workers learn conceptual and theoretical knowledge to effectively fulfill their responsibilities.

2.5 Staff Training and Staff Productivity

Training is invaluable in increasing productivity of organizations. This does not only enhance employees' resources but also provides them with an opportunity to virtually learn their jobs and perform more competently. Hence, increasing not only employee's productivity but also organizations' productivity. Various studies have indicated the positive impact of training on employee productivity.

Training as a process is one of the most widely used methods to enhance individuals' productivity and communicate organizational goals to personnel (Ekaterini & Constantinos-Vasilios, 2009). Rohan and Madhumita (2012) also supported the notion that investing in training employees on decision-making, teamwork, problem-solving, and interpersonal relations has a beneficial impact on the organizations' level of growth, as well as on employees' performance. Training affects employees' behavior and working skills, which results in enhanced employee performance and constructive changes (Satterfield & Hughes, 2007). Training is the most effective way to motivate and retain high-quality human resources within an organization (Kate Hutchings et al, 2009). Also added by Lowry, Simon, and Kimberley (2002), training is a way to enhance employee commitment and maximize employee potential.

According to Konings and Vanormelingen (2009), Colombo and Stanca (2008), and Sepulveda (2005), training is an instrument that fundamentally affects the successful accomplishment of organizations' goals and objectives. However, the optimum goal of every organization is to generate high revenue and maximize profits, and an efficient and effective workforce. Thus, a workforce is only efficient and effective if appropriate training and development are provided for such, leading to productivity (Rohan & Madhumita (2012).

2.6 Staff Development and Productivity

Development programs worth investing in because most successful organizations consider the progress of their workforce and therefore invest in their training. This results in increased skill and competence that improve morale and productivity (Sheeba, 2011). Development seems to reduce the turnover rate of employees (Deckop

et al, 2006). Thus, advancement opportunities do not only reduce absenteeism but also increase employee commitment and satisfaction, which helps reduce turnover (Atif et al, 2010).

3. Types of Training and Manpower Development Programs

There are many types of training and manpower development programs available. The particular method chosen by a university can be influenced by considering cost and time available, number of persons to be trained, depth of knowledge required and background of the trainee. Manpower development is a systematic process of training and growth through which individuals gain and apply knowledge, skills, insights, and attitudes and effectively manage work and personnel. This involves estimating the future demand for the supply of management staff at an organization. It is the involvement of efforts aimed at improving the quality as well as the number of management staff. Studies showed that many workers fail in organizational expectations because the training needs were not identified and provided for. Development may help to build confidence in workers and make them work more efficiently and effectively.

Training for job is received directly on the job, so it is often called "on-the job" training. It is used primarily to teach workers how to perform their current jobs. A trainer, supervisor, or co-worker serves as the instructor. When properly planned and executed, this method includes each learning principle (Demetra et al, 2008).

This is a widely accepted method of developing workers used by most organizations. According to Chim Obisi (1996:224), "old and experienced workmen perform much better in any organization when they undergo training and manpower development through on-the-job training programs". The advantage of this method is that it creates good working relationships because employees get to know each other better and the working environment. On the other hand, this method is disadvantageous in the sense that it could result in unorganized supervision, monotonous work, and the use of unqualified personnel for supervision when qualified individuals are undergoing training. On-the-job training could take the form of training by experienced workmen. It could also take the form of an apprenticeship, which is the oldest method of training.

In training and development methods, information presentation can be performed in various ways:

- (a) **Conference Method:** This could take the form of a seminar program in which a small group of people from different organizations is invited.
- (b) **Classroom Method:** It can be used to reach a large crowd, and it is usually two-way communication, where questions are asked and answered.
- (c) **Programed Instruction:** This involves teaching aides such as cassettes, films, etc. This method is different from the conventional form of training in which the trainer guides the process because the materials to be learned are presented in a way that the student can control.
- (d) **Lecture Method:** This is a student institutional method used in colleges, polytechnics, and universities. It is cheaper and can accommodate more students.
- (e) **Simulation Approach:** People are trained on real life experiences, i.e., problems that present in real life. The simulation approach involves a demonstration or role-playing method.
- (f) **Demonstration Method:** This method explains to trainees by teaching live examples, such as making displays. It is more about showing than telling the trainee, and that is why it is learning by seeing.
- (g) **Role Playing Method:** It is a technique in which real or imaginary problems involving human interaction are presented and then spontaneously acted out.

4. Need for Management Evaluation and Development

While reviewing discussions on the need for management evaluation and development, we noted that while some people feel that money is the foundation of a business, some scholars stress the need for human resource planning and management as the main essence of organizational survival and growth. Drucker (1980:130) is of the opinion that since no one can foresee further, management cannot make actual and responsible decisions unless it selects the men and women who will have to take care of these decisions.

Bawey (1977:23) emphasized that the most important factor underlying management evaluation is an understanding of human behavior and the resulting social process. This goes to buttress how environmental influence affects the behavior of workers which in turn affects productivity. Abel Ubeku (1975:34) feels that “forward looking” should be rule in every aspect of running a business. This is even more important when talking about adequate manpower and the right type of manpower, especially in countries where technical and managerial skills are lacking. According to him, the days of unsystematic and intuitive improvement in the use of manpower have come to a close. He sees management evaluation as part of the organization, which should not be seen in isolation.

However, in the context of the growth of the organization, management evaluation plays a key role in training and developing staff productivity. This covers more than simple planning of the manpower requirements of an organization since it hinges on all aspects of the business and is concerned with the future.

Corroborating the views of Ubeku, Oliver Ibekwe (1984:18) believed that a ‘forward looking’ plan ensures that the necessary human efforts to make possible survival and growth are available and entails manpower forecasting, which means gathering data in relation to labor, evaluating the data and making predictions on the future based on the data.

Abel Ubeku (1975:46) recognized two stages in management evaluation. These stages are alia:

Stage 1: This is concerned with the dictated manpower inventory of all types and levels (unskilled, skilled, supervisory and managerial) employed throughout the period of the manpower plan.

Stage 2: This also concerns the supply of manpower resources.

Consequently, Coleman (1970:86) views the process as being five (5) stages. The first step is to determine the organizational objectives and plan for the planning period. Second, it determines the gross manpower requirement for the planned period. The third stage involves acquiring manpower inventory or determining current in-house capability. The fourth stage defines the net manpower requirement during the planning period. This is obtained by deducting the manpower inventory from the gross requirements. The fifth and final stage takes care of programing, meeting the next manpower requirement. This includes expansion or internal adjustments to the present workforce.

According to Richard Johnson (1989:74), the purpose of skill training and retraining is to enhance individuals’ competency to meet the desired standard for present-day or potential assignments. He went further, asserting that training helps participants improve their performance in their activities. The reasons for the need to determine training are as follows:

- a) People will be more productive in their present jobs and ready for advancement.
- b) Because the success of an enterprise requires that everyone perform at its optimum level, this call is part of determining and meeting the specific needs of each individual, which should be translated into training.
- c) Because all good people regardless of organizational level can do a good job, want to do a good job, and will do a good job if given a chance.

This change comes in part through the provision of opportunities for individuals to improve their knowledge, skills, or attitudes. In doing so, the University increases productivity, and the individual advances his/her career. Gain, steps must first be taken to determine valid training needs. Because time, money, and effort can be wasted on training that is not based on valid present-day or emerging needs.

5. Techniques for Motivating and Evaluating Staff for Efficient Productivity

We would first clarify the concept of motivation. Several management scholars have given several definitions of motivation. According to Middle Most and Hitt (1981), "Motivation is the willful desire to direct one's behavior toward goals. The three key elements in this definition are willful desire (Person's choice), behavior, and goal-directed purpose in behavior.

Wallace and Andrews Zilagy (1994) opine that

Motivation is a dynamic process that motivates, energizes, directs, and determines behavioral changes. It must be understood from the onset that motivation includes not only rewards and punishment; it includes ideas, expectations, and experiences. regarding motivation, people mostly act according to their perception, not reality. Adumbrating further on the concept of motivation, Lakin Folajin (2001) discussed motivation as a term generally used when somebody is stimulated, the interest of a worker so as to be able to work and bring or breed efficiency in his work. Taking it to academic parlance, Luthans (1998) submits that Motivation is a process that starts with a physiological or psychological deficiency or need that activates behavior toward a goal or incentive. Furthermore, Ateman and Snell (1999) see motivation as the forces that energize, direct and sustain a person's effort. In being goal-oriented, Robbins (2001) defined motivation as the processes that account for an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence in efforts toward attaining a goal.

Succinctly put, therefore, motivation is incentive or enthusiasm, which is an important determinant of human behavior that moves individuals toward a goal and thus motivates performance. That is to say, motivation precipitates behavior, which leads to performance. This means (100%) people are positively motivated. This leads to positive behaviors. Thus, motivated behavior is goal-directed behavior, which is behavior resulting from internal drives. These internal devices or (tension) is the roof of motivation.

Hence, it is important for managers to motivate behavior to reduce these 'tension' even though it has been agreed that these motivation behavior are "innate". It should be stated that, at times, external forces can dominate and determine behavior. Yet, at other times, it is directed toward self-satisfaction. Most significantly, the behavior is directed to obtain the wants that satisfy the needs.

Ricky Griffin (1984) defined 'motivation' as a cyclical process affecting the inner needs that they want to satisfy. Although common human needs exist, each person also has their own particular needs. Our strong needs provide us with personal goals that satisfy our needs. The intensity of needs and driving varies widely from one person to another. It is the strongest drive. Therefore, the sound manager tries to recognize strong needs, especially those dominating individuals. By doing so, he/she is able to understand his/her subordinates/employees, and this will go a long way in achieving enterprise objectives.

Motivation is the encouragement of cash and kindness given to people in an organization to make them work well and willingly. Famous management theorists who have contributed to the theory of motivation include Maslow, Vroom, Herzberg, McClelland, and McGregor, among others, as stated in this project. Certain factors influence the effectiveness of motivation efforts, such as experience, desire, quoting, and timing. There has been much emphasis on the significance of monetary incentives, especially in present-day Nigeria. Some believe money is the only incentive desired by workers, and many compensation plans have failed because of an over-

emphasis on salaries and wages. But a lot of other things could motivate people, and Nigerians in particular, apart from money. However, the poverty level of a society influences how much money plays a motivating role. When proposing a motivation scheme for employees, it is important to recognize these wants. Therefore, in the following paragraphs, we attempt to identify some of the techniques for motivating employees based on their wants, which we mention below:

- a) **Pay:** This desire helps satisfy physiological, security, and egoistic needs. Employees need to believe that they are paid decent wages, which compares favorably with what is offered in other organizations. However, the design of monetary compensation systems is exceedingly complex. Because it satisfies multiple needs and cannot motivate the whole person.
- b) **Security of Job:** We are living in an age of automation. Machines are rapidly replacing human labor. Many people lose jobs for this reason. In Nigeria today, socio-economic problems make both the private and public sectors retrench workers. People no longer have confidence in any sector. This has greatly demoralized average Nigerian workers. To be effectively motivated, employees must constantly be assured of job security.
- c) **Credit for Work Done:** Excellent performance should be rewarded to improve the ego of the employee. This could include verbal praise, money, rewards for suggestions, awards, recognition for years of service, and honesty.
- d) **Opportunity to Advance:** Most employees want opportunities for personal growth and development to enable them to reach their maximum potential. This feeling is influenced by a cultural tradition of freedom and opportunity.

The following are some important aspects of motivation in an organization. They include:

- a) It energizes, intensifies, directs, and causes persistence in efforts to attain a goal.
- b) This leads to improvement in task performance by workers in an organization.
- c) Job enrichment leads to challenges, achievements, recognition, and responsibilities.
- d) This causes opportunities for personal growth and development among employees to enable them to reach their maximum potential.
- e) Motivation where employees are allowed to participate in management decision-making leads to self-esteem, as stated in Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

Training and development must be designed and delivered to meet the needs of all employees in such a way that the employees will not only be productive but also be satisfied. Training and development has a positive impact on employees in carrying out their work more effectively, increasing their interpersonal and technical abilities, teamwork, job confidence, and motivation (Kate Hutchings et al, 2009).

Training in organizations is key to unlocking potential growth and development opportunities to achieve a competitive edge (Rama V. & Nagurvali Shaik, 2012). Organizations train and develop their workforce to the fullest to enhance their productivity. Thus, knowledge, skills, and abilities are determinants of employee performance that organizations must continuously invest in to improve their employees' productivity. As Noe (2006) stated, organizations spend an enormous amount of money and time on training to aid employees in learning job-related competencies. Thus, it is important to fully provide results from training efforts (Dowling & Welch, 2005).

Training and development ultimately upgrade not only the productivity of employees but also of the organization. It has been rightly stated that employee development is the key to organizational sustainable development. Organizations must have employees who can quickly adapt to the ever-changing world market.

Companies must invest in ongoing employee training and development to keep employees and be successful. The 21st century will be favorable to those organizations that can learn faster and adapt to changes than their competitors. Training enhances employees' initiative and quality of work, thereby assisting them to be more committed to achieving organizational goals and objectives and, in turn, enhancing employees' effectiveness within an organization.

In summary, training and development impacting staff productivity has not only improved the wellbeing of universities but also aided the prosperity of most countries that have put into consideration the design and delivery of training and development of workforce at the national educational level. As national policies improve a nation's human capital, this optimally in turn results in the economic growth of the nation. However, it is recommended for management of universities to give training and development of employees a priority to get the best out of the workforce as well as improve university staff's productivity.

Sequel to the results of this study, the following recommendations are made, with the sanguinity that they will be helpful in the move to improve management evaluation of staff productivity:

- a) The personnel policy of the Nigerian University should be made within the reach of the Staff of the University.
- b) A personnel policy of the Nigerian University should be developed to benefit the Staff of the University.
- c) The personnel policy of the Nigerian University should be designed to positively influence Staff productivity.
- d) The University management should perform an effective implementation and monitoring of the personnel policy concerning the university staff.
- e) The Nigerian university should perform an effective evaluation of Staff productivity and development.
- f) University management should be very consistent in evaluating staff productivity and development.
- g) The university staff should inculcate moral and job ethics of sincerity in the training and development of staff productivity.
- h) University management should apply fairness and equity in training and development of Staff productivity.
- i) Prompt payment helps satisfy physiological, security, and egoistic needs. Employees need to believe that they are paid decent wages, which compares favorably with what is offered in other organizations. However, the design of monetary compensation systems is exceedingly complex. It serves to satisfy multiple needs and cannot alone motivate the individual.
- j) We are living in an age of automation. Machines are rapidly replacing human labor. Many people lose jobs for this reason. In Nigeria today, socio-economic problems make both the private and public sectors retrench workers. People no longer have confidence in any sector. This has greatly demoralized average Nigerian workers. To be effectively motivated, employees should be constantly assured of the security of their job.
- k) Credit for Work Done: Excellent performance should be rewarded to improve the ego of the employee. This could include verbal praise, monetary rewards for suggestions, awards, recognition for years of service, and honesty as a means of giving credit for work.
- l) Staff should have the opportunity to advance. Most employees want opportunities for personal growth and development to be able to reach their maximum potential. This feeling is influenced by a cultural tradition of freedom and opportunity.

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